

High-Frequency Modelling of Electrical Machine Windings Using Numerical Methods

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Abstract—This paper presents a method for predicting high-frequency behavior of rotating electrical machines. An approach using the Finite Elements (FE) method coupled with a circuit simulator is utilized to obtain the machine common-mode and differential-mode impedances over the frequency range of interest. The machine geometry, winding configuration and material characteristics are the input for the proposed process. 2D electrostatic FE simulation is used to obtain the capacitive couplings while a magnetodynamic FE approach is used to obtain the frequency-dependent resistances and inductances. These parameters are used in an equivalent circuit that represents the machine stator winding layout. A Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) is used as a case study machine to implement the method. The agreement between the simulated model and experimental results is presented assessing the accuracy of the method.

Index Terms—AC machines, finite element analysis, electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), frequency response

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, the trends in power converter design point towards the adoption of new wide band-gap semiconductors such as silicon carbide or gallium nitride transistors. One of the drawbacks of such technology lays on the increased high-frequency spectra of the electrical power supply, which derives from the higher switching frequencies and voltage gradients (dv/dt) compared with traditional converter technologies [1]. This increased high-frequency content can accentuate electrical machine failure and Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) problems [2]. Thus, prediction of the response of electrical machines to high-frequency signal excitation can ease the component and the whole system design already at early stages. High-frequency models can be used to predict phenomena such as electromagnetic emissions, leakage and bearing currents, and over-voltage transients on the machine terminals.

The already existing high-frequency models for electrical machines are either experimental data based or pure numerical models. The first type utilizes experimental impedance measurements and curve fitting methods to map the machine response [3]–[6]. On the other hand, numerical methods such as the Finite Element (FE) analysis can be exploited to model the machine response only using its material characteristics, geometry and winding configuration [7]–[11]. Measuring the real machine impedance response provides an increased degree of accuracy compared with purely numerical methods. However, numerical methods can be integrated earlier on the design

loop while experimental data based models need a physical prototype of the machine. A detailed winding high-frequency model applied to a real machine and mapping both Common-Mode (CM) and Differential-Mode (DM) responses has not been yet developed to the authors' knowledge.

The focus of this work is placed on the numerical modeling to early assess the impact of machine design decisions on the high-frequency response. This paper presents a method to build a detailed high-frequency model for electrical machine windings using multi-conductor transmission line theory. A Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) with real industry application is used as a case study. First, the parameters of the equivalent circuit are extracted by using the FE method. Then, the machine connections are used to build an equivalent circuit. This circuit is analyzed to obtain the impedance response of the machine over the frequency range of interest. The method outline is shown in Figure 1. The work is organized as follows. Section II poses the principles for equivalent circuit topology definition, section III describes the FE analysis used to obtain the model parameters, section VI defines the circuit assembly and section V shows and discusses the simulation results and their comparison with early experimental measurements.

II. EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT DEFINITION

The machine under analysis is a 3-phase 10/12 concentrated-winding Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) used in power-steering applications. Some characteristics of the machine can be found in Table I. Each stator phase comprises 4 coils, with two of them connected in series and two parallel branches. Figure 2 shows the machine cross-section and winding layout. End-winding conductors are not included since their length compared with the conductors surrounded by iron is negligible in the concentrated winding topology.

TABLE I
PMSM MACHINE DATA

Number of slots	12
Number of poles	10
Nominal power [kW]	0.5
Base speed [rpm]	1000
Magnet remanence [T]	1.35
Turns/layer	8

Fig. 1. Modelling method block diagram

The equivalent circuit is built following the multi-conductor transmission line principles [12] where each conductor in the stator winding is represented by a transmission line. Two conductors form a turn, several turns form a coil and, by assembling the coils following the machine connections, a phase is built. Transmission lines are characterized by per-unit length parameters which are distributed in space. These parameters are the resistance, inductance, capacitance and conductance. Shunt conductance is neglected in this work due to its multi-physical nature which hinders its numerical

computation [13], [14]. In addition, the material properties for its estimation are usually not provided by manufacturers and it has been demonstrated that it is the parameter with the less influence on high-frequency models [15].

The frequency range of interest greatly influences the topology of the equivalent circuit. In order to define the frequency band limits the high-frequency source is analyzed. The lower limit is defined by the switching frequency of the converter, which can be set at 10kHz. The highest frequency of interest is defined by the rise and fall times during a switching event. These can range from a few micro-seconds for silicon semiconductors to nano-seconds for wide band-gap semiconductors [16]. The cut-off frequency at which the amplitude of the high-frequency harmonics will start to rapidly attenuate can be computed following:

$$f_{cut-off} = \frac{1}{\pi\tau_r} \quad (1)$$

where τ_r is the rise or fall time assuming a symmetric trapezoidal switching signal. By assuming a value of 10ns for the rise time, the cut-off frequency is located around 30MHz and the maximum frequency of interest can be defined at 100MHz.

The spatially distributed parameters can be lumped in space depending on the electric signal wavelength (λ) and on the larger spatial dimension of the conductors. The wavelength is frequency dependent and it is defined by the media properties where the conductors are located. These properties depend on the dielectric material used for insulation and on the iron core. Considering that the largest spatial dimension of

Fig. 2. PMSM cross-section and winding layout

Fig. 3. Equivalent circuit for a coil with n conductors

the conductors is the stack length, the spatially distributed elements can be lumped in space forming several equivalent circuits per conductor. This follows the common rule of thumb which states that the wavelength must be approximately equal to ten times the larger spatial dimension at the maximum frequency of interest for the transmission line to be electrically short [17]. However, a limitation exists on the number of electrical elements to be simulated at a feasible computational speed and an approximation is made in order to keep the simplicity of the model. Thus, only one lumped-pi equivalent circuit per conductor is implemented. Figure 3 shows the equivalent circuit schematic for a coil with n conductors considering inter-turn capacitive and inductive couplings.

III. PARAMETER EXTRACTION USING FE METHODS

A. Electrostatic FE analysis

This subsection describes the method to obtain the capacitive parameters of the equivalent circuit. An electrostatic 2D analysis for capacitance extraction is used, having as input the slot geometry and the dielectric material characteristics. The governing equation used for the electrostatic FE solver is given by [18]:

$$-\epsilon \nabla V = \rho \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the permittivity of the homogeneous region, V is the electric potential and ρ is the charge density.

For each simulation only one of the conductors is excited at a time. The slot walls and the non-excited conductors are set at zero potential. By using the surface charge on each of the non-excited elements, the different ij entries of the matrix are computed following the relationship:

$$C_{ij} = \frac{q_i}{V_j} \quad (3)$$

where q is the surface charge density on the different elements.

Figure 4 depicts the slot geometry for electrostatic simulation including the indexes used for organizing the matrix entries. For the machine under study, the same permittivity value is applied to all insulation elements due to the lack of detailed information. A value of 3.5 relative permittivity typical of a standard polyamide is used for simulation. The

resultant capacitance matrix is shown in Figure 5. The off-diagonal entries represent the coupling between conductors while the diagonal terms are the capacitances between one conductor and the slot walls. Further details about 2D electrostatic simulation for capacitance extraction can be found in [19].

B. Magnetodynamic FE analysis

The method to extract the frequency dependent inductances and resistances is explained in this subsection. A 2D magnetodynamic FE analysis is used for extracting these parameters following the governing equation [18]:

$$\nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu(B)} \nabla \times a = -j\omega\sigma a + \hat{J}_{src} - \sigma \nabla V \quad (4)$$

with a the complex magnetic vector potential, σ is the electrical conductivity, \hat{J}_{src} the phasor transform of the applied

Fig. 4. Slot geometry and conductor indexes

Fig. 5. Capacitance matrix example for $\epsilon_r = 3.5$

source current, B the flux density and μ the magnetic permeability. This type of problem is solved in the frequency domain, where all AC quantities and a are expressed in phasorial notation.

The conductivity values are 2.38 MS/m and 59.6 MS/m for the electrical steel and the copper respectively. Relative permeability of the iron core is not directly provided and it can be extracted from the non-linear BH curve characteristic of the material.

The amplitude of the high-frequency excitation signals is normally very low compared to those at operation frequencies. For this reason the initial permeability value is normally adopted for the iron. This value represents the part of the non-linear BH curve where the walls motion is reversible and thus, it is lower than the permeability when the external magnetic field is high. However, this value is not valid for PMSMs which have a DC magnetic field created by the rotor magnets. This field affects the stator core permeability which will considerably increase. To obtain the iron core permeability

value, the B-field distribution in the stator at a fixed rotor position is evaluated. Figure 6 shows the contour plot of the stator B-field for a magnetostatic analysis with fixed rotor position. By averaging the B-field value over all the mesh elements in the stator a value of 0.29 T is obtained. The relative permeability of the stator at DC conditions can be obtained by using:

$$\mu_{r,DC} = \frac{B_{avg}}{H|_{B_{avg}} \mu_0} \quad (5)$$

where B_{avg} represents the average flux density in the stator, $H|_{B_{avg}}$ the magnetic field strength for the obtained average B-field and μ_0 the permeability of vacuum. By using the material BH curve and the obtained average B-field, the relative permeability at DC conditions results in 5630.

Another phenomena arise at high-frequencies affecting the iron core permeability. Eddy currents at operation frequencies

are minimized by using a laminated core but at high frequencies these currents will start flowing with little resistance within single laminations. These high frequency eddy currents cause an increased shielding effect which will affect the winding impedances. A 3D magnetodynamic simulation of the laminated iron core is required to obtain the frequency dependent parameters with high accuracy. However, this 3D FE analysis is not computationally feasible. To simplify the parameter extraction an equivalent 2D model is built taking into account eddy currents within single laminations. This is achieved by assimilating the laminated iron core to a solid, isotropic, non-conducting material having frequency dependent complex permeability. The real and imaginary parts of the effective complex permeability are [20]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{eff}(f) &= \mu_0(\mu'(f) - j\mu''(f)) \\ \mu'(f) &= \mu_{r,DC} \frac{\delta}{2b} \frac{\sinh(2b/\delta) + \sin(2b/\delta)}{\cosh(2b/\delta) + \cos(2b/\delta)} \\ \mu''(f) &= \mu_{r,DC} \frac{\delta}{2b} \frac{\sinh(2b/\delta) - \sin(2b/\delta)}{\cosh(2b/\delta) + \cos(2b/\delta)} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with δ the frequency dependent iron penetration depth and $2b$ the lamination thickness.

The geometry for computing the frequency dependent impedances is shown in Figure 7. Each single conductor is modeled to take into account skin and proximity effects. The mesh of the conductors is modified for each simulation frequency to account for the skin depth. The iron area is extended because the penetration depth in the iron is not solved due to the non-conduction assumption of the magnetic material. It is enough to consider the two closest adjacent slots to properly take into account the iron core effect. Mutual effects between conductors of different slots are not considered since the penetration depth at high frequencies is smaller than the tooth width. The lamination thickness for the case study motor is 0.5 mm. Conductors are numbered as in Figure 4 to organize the different impedances in frequency dependent matrices.

Each conductor is separately excited with a unit real-valued current for each frequency value. Figure 8 shows a contour

Fig. 6. Stator B-field distribution for a fixed rotor position

Fig. 7. Geometry for magnetodynamic FE analysis

Fig. 8. Current density absolute value contour plot and real flux lines when the 16-th conductor is excited ($f = 10$ kHz)

Fig. 9. Real (left) and imaginary (right) part of the impedance matrix ($f = 90$ kHz)

plot for the absolute value of the current density where the skin and proximity effects in the conductors are identified. The voltage drop on the excited and on the neighboring conductors represent the self and mutual impedances respectively. At a certain frequency the current will flow only on the conductor's surface and thus, the inductances can be assumed to be constant over frequency due to the small skin depth. In addition, solving the skin depth at very high frequencies can cause the simulation time to be excessively long. For these reasons the upper frequency limit for magnetodynamic simulation is kept at 10MHz. Results for higher frequency limits are obtained by using extrapolation. Figure 9 shows the real and imaginary parts of the impedance for every conductor in a slot at a single frequency point. The matrices show the higher value of the self impedance entries in the matrix diagonal compared with the mutual terms located in the off-diagonal.

IV. EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT ASSEMBLY

Each conductor inside the slots is connected forming coils. These coils are connected following the scheme in Figure 10 to

assemble the star-connected stator winding. Each parameter is assigned to the different conductors respecting their position in the slot and following the lumped-pi equivalent circuit topology. A Simulation Program with Integrated Circuit Emphasis (SPICE) is used to obtain the machine impedances over the frequency range of interest.

The frequency dependency of the self and mutual resistances and reactances is implemented by using the Laplace transform. They can be represented by a function of the shape $y(x) = ax^b + c$. This expression is selected as the outcome from a trade-off between accuracy, simplicity and method compliance. Thus, we can describe the frequency dependent behavior by using:

$$\begin{aligned} R(f) &= p_1 f^{p_2} + p_3 \\ X(f) &= p_4 f^{p_5} + p_6 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where p_n are the parameters used to build each curve over frequency. Figure 11 shows the representation and the curve fitting accuracy for the self-impedance of a conductor. The relative error for the fitting stays below the 15% , with an average error around 4% for the resistances and 3% for the reactances.

Fig. 10. Coil connection for the PMSM under study

Fig. 11. Self-impedance for a conductor. Fitted representation and relative error over frequency

Fig. 12. SPICE equivalent circuit with frequency dependent elements using Laplace transfer functions

Coefficient matrices containing the three p_n parameters for each conductor resistance and reactance are obtained. Then, it is possible to apply the Laplace transform to the frequency dependent expressions by using:

$$f = \frac{s}{j2\pi} \quad (8)$$

where s is the Laplace variable.

Two types of elements are used to include the Laplace expressions into the circuit. Self impedances are represented by voltage controlled current sources. The source current is defined by a transfer function and the voltage drop in the source according to:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{source} &= \frac{1}{G(s)} V_{source} \\ G(s) &= R(s) + jX(s) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $G(s)$ is the transfer function between the source voltage and current. The mutual impedance terms are represented by behavioral voltage sources. These sources emulate the mutual terms voltage drop by multiplying the current flowing through one conductor by the transfer function of the mutual-impedance $M(s)$. Figure 12 represents the equivalent circuit of a n conductor system using frequency-dependent circuit elements.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND MEASUREMENT

The model outputs are the CM and DM impedances over the frequency range of interest. The machine housing is assumed as the absolute ground point for both measurement and simulation results. Figure 13 describes the connection setup to obtain both motor impedances.

A LCR meter (BK Precision 895) with a 1MHz upper frequency limit is used to experimentally determine the impedance responses of the machine. The simulation and experimental results are shown in Figures 14 and 15 for CM and DM respectively.

The CM response shows a capacitive behavior over a large frequency range. The simulation data follow the same trend as the experimental results with a little offset in the amplitude. This means that the parasitic capacitances between the winding and the iron are the most important contribution to

the capacitive coupling. Improved accuracy could be obtained by taking into account the winding-rotor or the star point parasitic capacitance.

A more significant discrepancy is observed on the DM results. The amplitude data is located around the same impedance range. However, the phase agreement shows a difference of around 20° . This discrepancy could be a result of the homogenization technique used for simplifying the iron core model in the magnetodynamic FE parameter extraction. Another reason for the curve differences can be the absence of machine connection bars and end-winding in the model. The material properties obtained from manufacturer data sheets can also lead to differences both in the CM and the DM responses.

The simulation times are shown in Table II. These time data are heavily dependent on the number of frequency points considered for the simulation. For both the equivalent circuit and the magnetodynamic FE simulations 10 frequency points per decade have been considered. The most computationally expensive process is the magnetodynamic FE analysis.

Fig. 13. Impedance measurement and simulation setup. (a) CM, (b) DM

Fig. 14. CM impedance simulation result and experimental measurement

Fig. 15. DM impedance simulation result and experimental measurement

TABLE II
CASE STUDY SIMULATION TIMES

Equivalent circuit SPICE	70 s
Electrostatic FE	2 min 20 s
Magnetodynamic FE	5 h 27 min 49 s

VI. CONCLUSION

A method for high-frequency CM and DM machine impedance prediction has been presented. The method is based on the simulation of a detailed equivalent circuit of the stator winding using a SPICE software. The circuit parameters have been obtained by using electrostatic and magnetodynamic 2D FE simulation. Frequency dependency and mutual effects between conductors within the same slot have been taken into account for building the equivalent circuit. The simulation results have been compared with experimental measurements up to 1MHz and potential error sources have been identified. This method can be used at early stages of the design when a physical prototype of the machine is not yet available. In this way, it is possible to evaluate the impact of the design decisions on the high-frequency machine response. The usage of this type of model including frequency dependent parameters is limited to the frequency domain.

Future work on this topic includes the impedance measurement up to 100MHz by using an impedance analyzer. The iron core homogenization technique must be validated by comparing the results with a more sophisticated 3D model. The magnetodynamic FE simulation can be further simplified to reduce the simulation time. In addition, the machine configuration, geometry and material characteristics impact on the impedance responses can be studied and analyzed.

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